

Role of Perceived Organizational Support in Linking Employee-Oriented SR-HRM and Affective Commitment Among RMG Workers in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to determine how socially responsible human resource management affects the commitment of RMG employees in Bangladesh. Data was collected via a questionnaire survey from workers and employees of different RMG sectors in Dhaka and also through the online surveys using convenience sampling technique. With the use of an online survey, the questionnaire was created as a close-end survey with 5-point Likert scales. The questionnaire was divided into two sections, Section A displaying the respondents' demographic information, and Section B asking about the respondents' commitment to their jobs, compliance with the law, support for CSR initiatives, and HRM's employee orientation.

There were 150 respondents, and the SPSS version 21.0 was used to analyze the frequency distribution, coefficient, linear regression, and multiple regressions to interpret the variables utilized in this study. The projected results state that employee commitment in the RMG sectors will affect legal compliances in HR, CSR initiatives, employee-focused HRM, and general HRM facilities. By concentrating on the influence of inclusive SR-HRM in relation to employee commitment to RMG in the context of Bangladesh, the study adds to the body of existing literature in the subject. According to the results, there is a strong correlation between socially conscious HRM and employee commitment in Bangladesh's RMG industry.

KEYWORDS: Socially Responsible Human Resource Management, Employee Commitment, RMG Industry.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is not surprising that employee commitment is a fundamental activity for the success of an organization. An organization requires employee commitment to increase demand as it helps the organization to retain more staff and to achieve productivity and effectiveness. Employee commitment is now considered a natural process for effective performance of individuals and organizations (Armstrong, 2005). Organizations are striving hard to induce commitment in their employees. They are using different means and methods to enhance employee's commitment. Employee commitment has been an important factor to determine the success of an organization. Every employee has a desire to reach his self-actualization motivational level (Gul, 2015). Therefore, an employee must be given opportunities to improve his knowledge, skills and abilities. Employee development programs provide chances for promotion and career growth. Such activities in an organization create commitment in employees, which is a basic requirement for effective functioning of an organization.

An engaged employee is active, enthusiastic about their work, and performs in a way that advances the objectives of the organization. Top three factors influencing employee commitment are: fulfillment, fairness, and care & concern.

The relationship between socially responsible human resource management (HRM) has very recently become an interesting and productive/profitable area of research (Voegtlin & Greenwood, 2016). Companies that conceive and implement social responsibility have undoubtedly implications for both employees and human resources managers (Hassan, 2015). On the other hand, to motivate employees, favor commitment and organizational identification (Shen J. a., 2011), and define goals HRM can use to incentivize and reward employees or even introduce standards for decent work (Mariappanadar & Kramar, 2014). Currently, socially responsible human resource management (SRHRM) is emerging as a concept basically devised from two areas of research, the HRM and the budding CSR. Both of them are inevitably linked because of the socially responsible practices that have been formulated for stakeholder "employees," considering the guidelines of the HRM focused on promoting and improving employee well-being. Just as economic, social, and environmental practices attributed to a socially responsible firm that has a positive impact on firm performance through stakeholders' expectations achievement and the consequent concatenation of positive reactions (Agyemang & Ansong, 2017), the SR-HRM should have positive effects not only on employees but also on other stakeholders. The influence of three dimensions

of socially responsible human resource management are legal compliance HRM, employee-oriented HRM and general CSR facilitation HRM on employee’s organizational behavior.

This study has concentrated on the many issues that the apparel industries are currently facing. In order to obtain information on the current state of the apparel industries, as well as issues with and predictions for the future of the sectors, I have enlisted the help of a few reputable clothing firms. This topic in particular is very broad in scope. This paper made an effort to focus on the relationship between employee engagement, legal compliance, and CSR HRM on employees' organizational behavior. Although hard efforts were made to make the study worthwhile and significant, it nevertheless has several limitations. This study will also act as a useful resource for those who will be undertaking research on issues related to human resource practices on employee commitment with legal and CSR facilitation HRM on employee commitment and organizational behavior in garment sectors in Bangladesh.

1.4 Research Questions

- Is there any relationship between SR-HRM and employee commitment in the RMG industry?

2.LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Employee Commitment

Employee commitment defines an organization as a progressive competitive lever enabling the firm to achieve advantage over other businesses, this proves to be valuable for the said purpose. Employee commitment is therefore in hot pursuit in recent literature (Lee, 2016). He goes on to say that (Taneja, 2015) organizations can obtain competitive advantage through effectively and efficiently increasing their strategy of employee commitment. A dedicated and involved employee fully embraces his role and attempts at corporate goals, engages in inspiring peers towards realization of indeed substantial achievement. The perceived personal commitment is more than simply determination of executing their duties credits to contributing something positive in terms of assisting the entity function within its aspirations competitively. Individuals are capable of assuming responsibility at organizational levels which eventually results in attainment of strategic objectives long range (Rimi, 2013). It was found out that HRM has some important value as a source for sustained competitive advantage when viewed as a bundle or composite set with high commitment HRM practices (Rubel, Rimi, Yusliza, & Kee, 2018). These researchers argued also that it should be further addressed what reasonable human resource management practices mean for sustainability have significance.

Many of the observations were made from a perspective limited to Western countries. Numerous research efforts have

2.2 Socially Responsible of Human Resource Management

Socially responsible firms design their HRM practices not only to comply with local labour laws and international labour organization (ILO) standards, LC-HRM (Shen J. a. et al. 2011), such that firms comply with labor laws, and exceed them to invest in meeting the needs of employees as well as stakeholders in the community. Kilbourne and Rama (2017), EO-HRM, and GF-HRM, that is EO-HRM and especially the GF-HRM. LC-HRM relates to policies and practices designed to ensure that enterprises comply with laws and regulations concerning equal employment opportunity, occupational health and safety, working hours, minimum wage and child/forced labour. EO-HRM deals with employees’ personal and family issues and therefore is more than what is stipulated in the.

2.3 Relationship Between Human Resource Management Practices and Employee Commitment

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Companies use a variety of HR practices to improve efficiency and effectiveness, such as performance management, recruitment and selection, and training and development. (Darrag, Mohamed, & Aziz, 2010) stated successful companies need to use basic recruitment methods to attract the attention of relevant employees. However, according to Pasaoglu (2015), the responses of various companies to the recruitment and selection system are influenced by the specifics of the process, which have an effect on employees. (Maheshwari & Vohra, 2015) say that staff training focuses on skills that help them understand and be more committed to their work. It should be noted that this was proposed by (Idowu, 2017) to review the organization's HR practices, such as performance management. Numerous studies have demonstrated an important linkage between training and development. Satisfactory performance evaluation systems provide a comprehensive basis for analyzing employee performance and giving appraisals according to their strengths and weaknesses (Krishnaveni & Sripirabaa, 2009). It is seen that when employees see they are treated fairly by their firm through performance appraisal and proper rewards are given based on their performance, then they feel positive about their job and the company, which in turn increases their job satisfaction.

Numerous researchers have explored the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and TBL. HRMPs play a vital role in achieving sustainable goals of the firm and enhance its TBL performance. (Voegtlin & Greenwood, 2016) proposed a combined CSR-HRMP approach, which explains that the involvement of employees in CSR enhances the firm’s TBL performance. The social side of CSR-HRMP integration explains that both social and business demand is integrated because society and businesses are interdependent for growth and continuity. By boosting

employee morale, well-being, loyalty, and productivity, HRMPs can effectively improve the company's social performance. Implementation of HRMPs enhances the ability of firms in achieving goals and provides it with a competitive advantage, which in turn increases a firm's economic performance (Randev & Jha, 2019). Various HRMPs contribute positively to firms such as efficient and cost-effective recruitment, development of staff skills and managing employee performance (Indiparambil, 2019). In addition, they provide an organization with a structure that encourages employees to participate in organizational activities and provides ongoing feedback. According to Taneja (2015), performance management enables businesses to evaluate each employee's performance, which aids in employee development and ultimately results in higher company performance. Among the literature on HRMPs and economic performance, a positive relationship can be observed due to cost reductions and goal completion, resulting in enhanced financial performance (Randev & Jha, 2019).

According to (Porter, Bigley, & Steers, 2003) an engaged workforce generates valuable business results for an organization. The process starts with employer practices such as job and task design, recruitment, selection, training and development, compensation, performance management and career development. Such practices affect employees' level of commitment. According to (Wickramasinghe & Samaratunga, 2016) the role of human resources has changed greatly since medieval times when the major motivational factors were basic human necessities and the role of human resource was to arrange for these in proportion to the work done. (Darrag, Mohamed, & Aziz, 2010) asserts that today's company should consist of fast, flexible and dynamic teams of enthusiastic, motivated, creative and fully self-expressed people. According to (Porter, Bigley, & Steers, 2003), human resource will have to play a substantial role in the business in order to perform these role human resource professionals should have: Thorough knowledge of business as well as of human resource functions, the ability to lead any change process, innovation, problem solving, the leadership ability to influence the organization, since there are different sets of people who have different expectations, there have to be newer roles and newer competencies of human resources.

2.4 Legal Compliance Human Resource Management on Employee Commitment

Human resources hires employees and regularly interacts with and trains them. Most importantly, HR is crucial in fostering an environment of accountability, which is the foundation for compliance. HR therefore plays a crucial role in corporate compliance initiatives because of its enormous effect over compliance. The process of defining both individual and group behaviors to guarantee the organization's compliance with the laws and policies that apply should be considered HR compliance (Armstrong,

2005). The HR function must employ and keep on staff people who are familiar with HR-specific regulations and who can draft policies and procedures in accordance with those laws. It is not sufficient to simply write down policies and procedures and save them in a repository. They must be successfully conveyed throughout the firm after they are developed.

This is most likely to occur, according to Voegtlin & Greenwood (2016), when HR compliance has been integrated into the organization's overall business strategy and the leadership has taken steps to ensure that all employees are aware of its significance. Here are five basic principles organizations should follow to help achieve these goals:

Finding the Right People in the HR Function's Responsibilities (Pay, Employee Perks, Legal Obligations, Talent Management) is One of Today's Most Important Challenges for Businesses. The HR function must possess the necessary information, abilities, and experience, or have the connections to get it from outside sources.

Proper Education and Training – The HR function's talent must be knowledgeable about employment law and the regulatory and legal requirements that may at any time have an impact on an enterprise. The HR function must constantly be aware of the most recent information because these regulations and requirements are constantly evolving. The employee handbook should clearly outline the company's policies, procedures, and expectations for conducting business. It should also be regularly updated as a communication tool. Having legal counsel examine the handbook and any new policies and procedures before distribution is recommended practice. One of an organization's most important documents is the employee handbook.

Conducting Scheduled HR Compliance Audits – Many HR functions are typically understaffed and overworked. As noted, non-compliance can lead to concerns for an organization's finances and reputation. An organization's overall strategy to stay out of legal trouble should include scheduling HR compliance audits. Communicate, Communicate and Communicate – The HR function is a critical component of an organization. The HR function leaders must inform other executives of any potential risks to HR compliance and the suggested remedies, whether or not there are any compliance issues.

2.5 Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Simplification Human Resource Management on Employee Commitment

Employees are one of the most important stakeholders of any organization. Since they can be affected by and also affect their organizational activities, the employees play a key role in the success or failure of their organization. According to Elçi & Alpan (2008), this is how employees are likely to be affected by the CSR programs and react differently at work. According to Ashforth & Mael (1989), the connection

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between employees' attitudes and behaviors and perceptions of CSR is supported by social identity theory (SIT) and social exchange theory (SET). Employee perception of the work environment has drawn a lot of attention from researchers in organizational literature. Individual performance has been seen to be influenced by psychological interpretations of an organization's activities, such as OCB (Moorman, 1991) and job performance (Ashforth & Mael, 1989). Employee CSR perception refers to employees' personal evaluations and interpretations of an organization's CSR activities, which may differ from the actual CSR practices of the organization. Employee perception is subjective; it represents the employees' interpretation of an organization's activities and sense-making process (Wright & Nishii, 2004). Employees' attitudes and behaviors are influenced by this perception.

"Commitment is not an attitude; it is the degree to which an individual is attentive and absorbed in the performance of their roles," states Moore (1991). Rather than extra-role and voluntary behaviors, formal role performance is the focus of commitment. According to Kular, Gatenby, Rees, Soane, & Truss (2008), job involvement is the psychological presence of an individual in his or her job-related role, whereas organization commitment is the employee's commitment to carrying out his or her role as a member of the organization. Performance of CSR by the organization may provide a higher sense of meaningfulness in the job in the sense that the employees may feel they are not working for the organization simply for their bread and butter; rather, they are part of an

institution that serves the community to make the world a better place to live in. (Albdour & Ikhlas, 2012) found a positive correlation between employees' perceptions of internal CSR and their engagement in their jobs and organizations, but their study did not take into account any mediating factors.

2.6 Research Objectives

The research's overarching goal is to determine how employee commitment to the apparel industry is affected by socially responsible human resource management, employee orientation, CSR initiatives, and legal compliance within the organization. The study's specific objectives are as follows:

- ✚ To find out how employee commitment is affected by HRM that is focused on the employee.
- ✚ To examine the effect of HRM compliance with legal requirements on employee commitment.
- ✚ To understand the importance of general CSR facilitation HRM on employee commitment

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In accordance with the hypothesis, the conceptual framework depicts the independent and dependent variables for the analysis, with employee commitment serving as the dependent variable and employee oriented, legal compliance, and general CSR facilitation serving as the independent variables.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Research Design

Research Methodology Both primary and secondary sources of information were used in the research for this study. The majority of the study's participants worked full-time jobs for Bangladesh based companies. There is a written CSR strategy for each of the RMG businesses that made up the organizations. This study used a cross-sectional and quantitative research approach in order to describe the impact of socially responsible human resource management on employee commitment in the RMG industry in Bangladesh.

4.2 Sample Size

For conducting the survey, employees and managers from different industries were selected as a sample size to enhance the productivity by their own engagement as well as the engagement of their subordinates. From 10 RMG firms, 150

supervisor personnel were identified as the study's final respondents.

In the ready-made clothing sector of Bangladesh, approximately 5000 RMG businesses employ approximately 50 million individuals. This investigation's sample size was therefore determined using Yamane's formula. Around 200 garment workers from the ten firms under investigation were interviewed for this study; 150 of the respondents provided responses, and the task was then completed in accordance with their comments.

4.3 Sampling Design

The data for this report were gathered through the use of a quantitative survey. Employee commitment is the dependent variable, and employee-oriented HRM, HRM for legal compliance, and general CSR facilitation are the independent variables. Determine the relationships between the dependent

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and independent variables, as well as their effects on the study, using the Multiple Regression Equation.

4.4 Sampling Technique

This study was conducted using the convenience sampling technique, in which the researchers gather market research data from a pool of respondents who are readily available. In circumstances when there are sizable populations, researchers employ a variety of sampling strategies. Because they are difficult to reach, testing the entire community is nearly impossible most of the time. When additional inputs are not required for the main inquiry, researchers employ convenience sampling.

As the time is constraint, using a convenience sampling technique is better due to researchers choosing members merely based on proximity and doesn't consider whether they represent the entire population or not. Using this technique, they can observe habits, opinions, and viewpoints in the easiest possible manner. So, having to choose a convenient sampling technique, it is easier to collect data, inexpensive to create samples, easy to do research with low cost and readily available samples for the researcher.

4.5 Research Instruments

Three independent variables are employee oriented HRM, legal compliances, and CSR facilitation HRM, have been selected for this study.

Table 1: Research Instrument

Variable Names	Sources
Employee Orientation	(Human Resource Management Practices Questionnaire, n.d.)
Legal Compliances	(Human resource surveys and sample HR questions, n.d.)
CSR Facilitation	(Shen & Benson, 2014)

4.6 Techniques for Collecting Data

The methodology chosen is based on assuming that collected data through a survey is simple to perceive and thus considered as valid. Moreover, the use of the questionnaire allows for greater control over the research procedure. After working closely with HRM, the respondents for the survey were carefully selected. A Five-point Likert scale questionnaire, for instance (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree), was sent to the managers, employees and subordinators in the RMG industries. Some of the surveys were conducted personally by me while I visited a few of the RMG industries to conduct them, while others were collected through personal communication with the garment workers' association, and the questionnaires were translated into Bangla so that employees could respond effectively. The questionnaire consisted of two parts, the first section consists of the respondent information, along with experience, qualification, and department. In the second section, the HRMP question, relationship commitment, manager involvement, and employee commitment are all discussed.

4.7 Methods for Analyzing Data

The data is analyzed using a quantitative method. In order to guarantee the efficiency of the data and limit the rate of error, questionnaires were coded for each study variable, and precision was ensured during the analysis. The survey is well structured and is based on Likert scales from 1–5, whereas strongly disagreed-1; disagreed-2; Neutral-3; agreed-4; strongly agreed-5. (Human Resource Management Practices Questionnaire, n.d.)

4.8 Data Analyzing Tools

The data were analyzed by using SPSS for Windows 21.0 program to describe the strength of the association between

the variables. Definite statistical methods were used to evaluate the data. The linear regression is commonly used to explain the relationship between two or more independent variables and a continuous dependent variable. It showed the connection among the variables in order to make a prediction or estimate. As a result, a linear regression has been used to do the calculation of the combined impact of the independent variables on the dependent variable. Finally, multiple regression analysis was used to test the proposed hypothesis. Demographic statistical results on legal compliance, employee engagement, and CSR facilitation have been analyzed in the context of the RMG sector of Bangladesh. The sample comprised information from 150 people who engaged in responding questionnaires from various RMG industries.

This chapter represents the findings and analysis from the data gathered for the study. Demographic data are done which shows the respondents' descriptive characteristics, which are presented first, then followed by descriptive statistics for employee commitment, legal compliance, CSR implementation, employee performance that has been considered as the Independent Variable and Employee Engagement as the Dependent Variable Finally, multiple regression analysis was used to test proposed hypotheses. The data was also analyzed using the IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 20.0 program. Tables and figures have been used to display the results.

5. FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

5.1 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

This section turns around analyzing the selected sample's demographic characteristics like age, gender, educational qualification, marital status. The tables are in the below:

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Table 2: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Demographic Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
Below 20	38	25.3%
20-30	53	35.4%
30-40	30	20%
40-50	23	15.3%
Above 50	6	4%
Total	150	100%
Gender		
Male	67	45%
Female	83	55%
Total	150	100%
Marital status		
Married	96	64%
Unmarried	54	36%
Total	150	100%
Education Qualifications		
SSC	33	22%
HSC	105	70%
BBA/Honors	8	5.3%
MBA/Masters	4	2.7%
Total	150	100%
Length of the service in the present Organization		
Less than 5	34	22.7%
6-10	88	58.6%
11-15	19	12.7%
15-20	6	4%
More than 20	3	2%
Total	150	100%

From the above table it can be concluded that most of the respondents are in the age of 20 to 30 (35.4%) years, more than half of the respondent are female (55%), most of them

are married (64%), 70% of respondents have the HSC degree and lastly the employees working within the industries are working are around 6 to 10 years (58.6%).

5.2 Descriptive Statistics

Parameter	Employee Oriented (EO)	Legal Compliance (LC)	General CSR Facilitation (GCSR)
N	150	150	150
Mean	4.540	4.323	4.456
Std. Deviation	.697	.575	.457

Figure 1: Descriptive Analysis

In the above table of descriptive statistics 4 columns are shown, where on the first column there's the parameter of N, Mean and Standard Deviation and second, third and fourth column show the values of N, Mean and Standard Deviation

of the variables, Inclusive employee oriented, legal compliance and general CSR facilitation respectively.

5.4 Results of Linear Regression Analysis

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5.4.1 Objective one: To test the Effect of Employee Oriented HRM on Employee Commitment of RMG Sector in Bangladesh

A single linear regression was used to analyze and fulfill this objective:

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.635 ^a	.405	.391	.35271

a. Predictors: (Constant), employee oriented HRM

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.224	1	4.224	31.345	.000 ^a
	Residual	6.513	46	.803		
	Total	10.437	47			

a. Predictors: (Constant), employee oriented HRM

b. Dependent Variable: Employee Commitment

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.206	.226		5.269	.000
	Employee Oriented HRM	.471	.083	.631	7.460	.000

Regression analysis results in the Model Summary table shows that Employee Oriented HRM that was selected for 40.5% on employee commitment which was indicated by r-squared of 0.405 implying that to small extent of employee oriented to HRM as a system to employee commitment in Bangladesh RMG sector.

The ANOVA table indicates that Employee Oriented as a system of HRM significantly affects the employee commitment and this was indicated by the F value=31.345 and Sig-value = .000, since the sig. value (0.000) was less than 0.05 which is the maximum level of significance required to declare a significant effect. This indicates that employee oriented as a system of HRM highly contributes to the employee commitment in Bangladesh RMG Sector.

The coefficients table indicates that considering the standard error, employee oriented significantly influences the employee commitment (Beta .471, Sig=.000). Giving that the Sig-Value (0.000) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Decision on Hypothesis

H1: Variable 1 is positively related to variable 4.

Ho: Variable 1 is not positively related to variable 4.

5.4.2 Objective two: To test the Effect of Legal Compliance HRM on Employee Commitment of RMG Sector in Bangladesh

A single linear regression was used to analyze and fulfill this objective:

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Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.569 ^a	.318	.313	.37723

a. Predictors: (Constant), legal compliance HRM

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.461	1	3.361	22.337	.000 ^a
	Residual	6.912	46	.133		
	Total	10.437	47			

a. Predictors: (Constant), legal compliance HRM

b. Dependent Variable: Employee Commitment

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.511	.212		6.378	.000
	Legal Compliance HRM	.377	.079	.461	4.512	.000

Here, the Model Summary table indicated that legal compliance HRM accounted for 31.8% on employee commitment in Bangladesh RMG Sectors and this was indicated by R-squared of .318 implying that legal compliances as a system of HRM significantly contributes 31.8% on the employee commitment in Bangladesh.

The ANOVA table indicates that legal compliance HRM significantly affects employee commitment indicated by the F-value=22.337 and Sig-value = .000, since the sig. value (0.000) was less than 0.05 and which is the maximum level of significance required to declare a significant effect. This implies that legal compliance as a system of HRM highly affects employee commitment of the RMG sector in Bangladesh.

The coefficients table indicated that considering the standard error, legal compliance significantly influences the employee commitment (Beta .471, Sig=000). Giving that the Sig-Value (0.000) is less than 0.05, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Decision on Hypothesis

H1: Variable 2 is positively related to variable 4.

Ho: Variable 2 is not positively related to variable 4.

5.4.3 Objective three: To test the Effect of General CSR Facilitation on Employee Commitment of RMG Sector in Bangladesh

A single linear regression was used to analyze and fulfill this objective:

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Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.611 ^a	.399	.391	.35975

a. Predictors: (Constant), general CSR facilitation

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.291	1	4.291	32.108	.000 ^a
	Residual	6.165	46	.131		
	Total	10.457	47			

a. Predictors: (Constant), general CSR facilitation

b. Dependent Variable: Employee Commitment

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.196	.235		5.365	.000
	General CSR Facilitation	.412	.76	.631	5.452	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Commitment

Regression analysis results in the Model Summary table revealed that general CSR facilitation accounted for 39.9% of employee commitment was indicated by r-squared of .399 implying that training and development as a strategy of HRM contribute to employee commitment of RMG sector in Bangladesh.

The ANOVA table indicated that general CSR facilitation as a strategy of HRM significantly affects employee commitment in Bangladesh and this was indicated by the F-value=32.108 and Sig-value = .000, since the sig. value (0.000) was less than 0.05 which is the maximum level of

significance required to declare a significant effect. This implies that general CSR facilitation as a strategy of HRM highly contributes to employee commitment in Bangladesh.

The coefficients table indicated that considering the standard error, general CSR facilitation significantly influences the employee commitment in Bangladesh (B=0.412, Sig=0.000). Given that the p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Decision on Hypothesis

H1: Variable 3 is positively related to variable 4.

Ho: Variable 3 is not positively related to variable 4.

5.5 Result of Multiple Regression Analysis

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.766 ^a	.544	.529	.34179

a. Predictors: (Constant), employee oriented HRM, legal compliance HRM and general CSR facilitation

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	26.987	3	8.996	28.503	.000 ^a
	Residual	33.770	107	.316		
	Total	60.757	110			

a. Predictors: (Constant), employee oriented HRM, legal compliance HRM and general CSR facilitation

b. Dependent Variable: Employee commitment

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	30.571	.212		2.698	.004
	Employee Oriented HRM	.339	.078	.337	3.942	.000
	Legal Compliance HRM	.301	.086	.335	3.841	.000
	General CSR Facilitation	.246	.088	.244	2.663	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Employees commitment

The Multiple regression analysis results in the Model Summary table shows that HRM practices (independent variables) accounted for 54.4% of employee commitment indicated by r-squared of 0.544 implying that HRM practices contribute to employee commitment of RMG sector in Bangladesh.

The ANOVA table indicated that HRM practices significantly affects employee commitment in the RMG sector and this was indicated by the F-value=28.503 and Sig-value = .000, since the sig. value (0.000) was less than 0.05 which is the maximum level of significance required to declare a significant effect. This implies that the employee oriented, legal compliances and general CSR facilitation of HRM practices highly contribute to employee commitment in the organization.

The coefficients table indicates that considering the standard error, HRM practices such as employee oriented, legal compliances and general CSR facilitation at 30.571. A Unit increase in employee oriented would lead to an increase in employee commitment by factor of 0.339 at 0.000; A Unit increase in legal compliances would lead to an increase in employee commitment by factor of 0.301 at 0.000, A Unit increase in general CSR facilitation would lead to an increase in employee commitment by factor of 0.246 at 0.001 at RMG sectors of Bangladesh. Therefore, employee oriented HRM has the biggest influence and a positive change on employee commitment at RMG sectors (B=.337, Sig=0.000).

Based on the findings the Null-hypothesis was rejected and therefore, it can be said that it significantly affects employee commitment on employee performance since the significant value is less than 0.05.

5.6 Discussion of Findings on the Effect of Employee Oriented on Employee Commitment

The findings of the study on the effect of employee oriented on employee commitment, revealed that majority of the respondents said that they were well informed about the jobs before being employed and practices to the new joiners and beneficial in developing realistic job expectations, that all the information they received at the recruitment process about the job was accurate, that the recruitment process was impartial and candidates were recruited on merit, and that qualifications and experience were considered in selecting the best suited candidates for recruitment and employers were educate employees regarding their role, key result areas and organizations expectations in advance to curb attrition at the later stage, during a skills dialogue session. With average mean and standard deviation scores of 4.54 and .697 respectively, the results imply that respondents strongly agreed that employee oriented having a positive and significant effect on employee commitment of RMG sectors in Bangladesh as employers with effective orientation programs have found that new employees stay longer.

5.7 Discussion of Findings on the Effect of Legal Compliance on Employee Commitment

The findings of the study on the effect of legal compliances on employee commitment, revealed that respondents said that there are various significant positive relationships between commitment and the perception that a fairness motive underlies personnel/human resource management activities. HRM activities are motivated by justice and fairness is positively associated with organizational commitment. The perception that HRM activities are motivated by a desire to attract or retain employees is also positively correlated with organizational commitment. On the other hand, there is a relationship between commitment and the number of HRM activities done to encourage increased performance or to comply with the law. With average mean and standard deviation scores of 4.32 and .575 respectively, the results imply that respondents agreed that legal compliance processes have a positive and significant effect on employee commitment in Bangladesh of RMG sectors.

5.8 Discussion of Findings on the Effect of General CSR Facilitation on Employee Commitment

The findings of the study on the effect of general CSR facilitation on employee commitment, revealed that respondents said that employee attitudes and behaviors will be affected by organizational culture and climate, by whether CSR policies are couched in terms of compliance or in terms of values, and by whether such policies are integrated into business processes or simply an ‘add-on’. Motivation and commitment will be affected by the extent to which they can align personal identity and image with that of the organization, by their perceptions of justice and fairness both in general and in terms of how CSR performance is rewarded,

and by their impressions concerning the attitude of top management to CSR issues and performance. With average mean and standard deviation scores of 4.45 and .457 respectively, the results imply that respondents strongly agreed that CSR facilitation with employee commitment of RMG sectors in Bangladesh as employers with CSR practices having various attitudes and behaviors of employees, such as their motivation at work, their confidence in the company and their commitment to it.

6. CONCLUSION

SRHRM is important not only for the employees but also for the organization because it influences employee’s commitment towards the organization for which this study was conducted to understand the employee commitment in accordance with the organization’s employee orientation, legal compliances and the general CSR facilitation of the SRHRM practices of RMG sectors in Bangladesh. From the correlation it has been observed the three independent variables made significant individual contributions to the prediction of organizational employee commitment. It can be said HRM programs, activities, policies and practices are means through which organizational people can be managed to gain competitive advantage.

The study's findings, which were stated above in the preceding chapter, support the notion that both factors have a mediating role in the relationship between organizational commitment and CSR. HRM procedures like these are included in SRHRM, which will assist the organization in determining the level of employee commitment. When the employees feel they have been recruited and selected properly, are being provided training for their betterment, are being compensated and appraised fairly, they display their vigor, their happiness and concentration in their work for the organization and their dedication towards the success of the organization. This highlights their engagement towards the organization. Finally, each and every company in the garment Industry should have proper and organised HRM policies and their practices in their every functional level of operation that will ensure the development of the Garments Industry of our country.

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